

Decision Making for Planetary Landing Applications using AI Agents and Reinforcement Learning

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This study explores the decision making capabilities of Large Language Model (LLM) AI agents to automate learning in planetary landing missions. In particular, the work investigates the use of AI agents to minimise human intervention in training a lunar lander by providing high-level strategic guidance to a Reinforcement Learning (RL) agent within the complex environment of Kerbal Space Program. To that end, LLM AI agents are utilised to interpret a lander manual and extract information for designing the rewards function of the RL algorithm, as well as to assess the training process and refine the rewards. A case study is conducted, comparing the performance of three types of LLMs, GPT-3.5-Turbo, GPT-4, and Meta-LLama-3-70B, in lunar landing tasks. The findings highlight the potential of interactive LLM agents for automated reward function generation and refinement, thus advancing AI capabilities in space exploration and autonomous navigation tasks.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Planetary landing presents a multitude of challenges that require real-time decision-making. Complex orbital mechanics, extreme landing environments, constrained on-board power and fuel, and the ever-present risk of catastrophic failures demand a combination of scientific knowledge, creative problem-solving, and real-time adaptation. Real-time decision-making and precise navigation are essential for ensuring safe and successful landings, especially in environments where human intervention is impractical or impossible. The use of LLMs has emerged as a promising approach to imitate human-like decision-making.

This study investigates the use of advanced LLMs to enhance the RL agent's training for safe lunar landings using a complex simulation environment (Kerbal Space Program). The innovative approach integrates LLM AI agents to interpret a lander manual and construct the rewards function for the RL algorithm. An Evaluator AI agent assesses the training process to refine the rewards function, improving the agent's landing performance.

To benchmark this approach, a comprehensive case study is conducted, comparing the performance of GPT-3.5 Turbo [1], GPT-4 [2], and LLama-3-70B [3] on the lunar landing task. The results indicate that GPT-4 achieves the highest performance, highlighting the significance of advanced language models in autonomous decision-making tasks.

1.2 Related Work

Several recent studies have demonstrated the potential of LLMs to assist and accelerate the learning process in RL algorithms. These approaches often involve extracting knowledge from human-written manuals or instructions. The authors in [4] have proposed a "Read and Reward" framework that utilises an LLM with a Q&A Extraction Module and a Reasoning Module. This framework extracts knowledge from Atari game manuals and significantly improves performance in Atari games with reduced training data compared to state-of-the-art methods. Other works, such as [5] and [6], demonstrate the effectiveness of LLMs in assisting embodied agents with complex decision-making tasks by providing high-level instructions.

Within the domain of RL for lunar landing, research has explored various frameworks for achieving successful soft landings. In [7], Xu et al. investigates the application of Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG), Twin Delayed DDPG (TD3), and Soft Actor Critic (SAC) for soft landing control algorithms. The

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authors demonstrated the effectiveness of RL in this domain and highlighted the challenge of defining an appropriate reward function for achieving algorithmic convergence.

The recent work by Rodriguez et al. [8] showcases the application of LLMs for spacecraft control within the Kerbal Space Program Differential Games (KSPDG) challenge [9]. The research utilised OpenAI’s GPT-3.5 to develop an LLM-based agent capable of manoeuvring spacecraft in pursuit-evasion scenarios within the KSPDG environment.

In the context of LLM-generated reward functions, while the work in [10] demonstrated the use of LLMs in combination with evolutionary algorithms for optimisation, the present study employs two interacting LLM agents within an agentic workflow framework. The agents generate and refine rewards through human-like reasoning and the prompts are limited to defining the inputs and the goals.

This body of prior work establishes a foundation for the present investigation into how LLMs can be leveraged to enhance RL-based decision making for planetary landing applications. This research contributes to the cutting-edge of AI-driven space exploration and autonomous navigation. It builds upon these advancements by exploring the potential of LLMs in guiding the training process of an RL agent for a successful lunar landing mission within the complex environment of KSP. To the knowledge of the authors, this is the first publication of its kind, aiming to lay the groundwork for more efficient and reliable autonomous spacecraft operations.

2 Proposed Solution

2.1 RL Environment

Kerbal Space Program (KSP) provides an excellent platform for simulating complex planetary landing environments due to its highly realistic physics engine. This software allows for the creation of custom scenarios that closely resemble the challenges of real-world space missions.

Using a realistic physics engine is essential for simulating spacecraft manoeuvres, especially during the descent phase of a planetary landing. KSP’s physics engine accurately models the effects of gravity, thrust, and atmospheric drag, providing a challenging, yet realistic environment for testing autonomous landing algorithms. The KSP environment used in this study is *Mun Orbit*, illustrated in Figure 1.

OpenAI’s Gym [11], a powerful toolkit for RL research, was used to build a custom environment specifically designed for KSP to perform RL-based lu-

nar landing. This was achieved by making use of the kRPC API [12]. Past experiments have successfully been demonstrated using RL for teaching rockets how to launch into orbit using KSP as environment [13].

Figure 1: KSP Mun Orbit environment.

2.2 RL Training

A Deep Q-Network (DQN) architecture is employed for RL training, as depicted in Figure 2. DQN is a deep RL method which utilises neural networks to approximate the Q-function. This function estimates the expected future rewards (R) for actions (a) taken in a particular state (s), guiding the agent to choose actions that maximise cumulative reward.

Figure 2: The architecture of a DQN.

The Q-function is represented as:

$$Q_{\text{New}}(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow Q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha [R_{t+1} + \gamma \max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a) - Q(s_t, a_t)], \quad (1)$$

where $Q(s_t, a_t)$ represents the Q-value of taking action a_t in state s_t , α is the learning rate, R_{t+1} is the immediate reward received after taking action a_t , γ is the discount factor, and $\max_a Q(s_{t+1}, a)$ represents the maximum expected cumulative reward that can be obtained by taking any action in the next state.

An epsilon-greedy strategy is used to balance exploration and exploitation during training. This strategy controls the agent’s behaviour by selecting random actions with probability ϵ and exploiting the learned policy with probability $1 - \epsilon$. As training progresses, ϵ gradually decreases, shifting the agent’s focus from

exploration to exploitation based on accumulated experience.

The kRPC API enables retrieval of various flight parameters, vessel status, orbital dynamics, and more. In this research, a comprehensive set of variables is extracted to evaluate the state of the agent. The observation state vector is composed of surface speed and altitude, while the action space consists of throttle settings with three values: [0, 0.5, 1]. Due to the time required for RL training, the landing scenario is limited to the final 500 meters of the last stage of descent.

2.3 Implementation approach

The proposed method involves two key AI agents:

- Interpreter (Knowledge Extractor):** This agent extracts crucial knowledge regarding the behaviour of the lander in the lunar lander environment from a lunar landing manual. Specifically, the interpreter focuses on dissecting the expected nominal behaviour of the lander’s rate of descent [m/s] versus altitude [m]. The lunar lander manual referenced in this study is the publication authored by Allan Y.Lee [14], which includes flight data reconstructed from the Apollo-11 Guidance, Navigation, and Control System Performance Analysis Report [15].
- Evaluator (Reasoning module and Software Expert):** This agent implements the Python rewards function for the RL training algorithm based on the expert knowledge provided by the interpreter and observations regarding the environment during training. Its role is to re-evaluate the rewards function and provide a refined version to enhance the convergence of the DQN.

The agents are collaborating using CrewAI [16], a frameworks which provides the backbone for sophisticated multi-agent interactions. The detailed workflow of the proposed method is illustrated in Figure 3 and the three main tasks are described in detail in Algorithm 1.

The workflow begins with the Interpreter (Task 1), which extracts relevant information from the lunar landing manual and provides it to the Evaluator. The Evaluator (Task 2) then generates a rewards function based on this information, which is utilised in the RL training algorithm (Task 3) to guide the agent’s behaviour. The following flight states are identified in the training environment: *Descending*, *Surface contact* (touchdown), *Ascending* (overuse of thrusters, bouncing off the surface of the Moon during landing, or running out of fuel), *Crashed*, *Landed at angle* (not landed

vertically), and *Landed*. The last four states also result in terminating the training episode, initiating a restart of the KSP environment. The flight states, along with an abstract class for rewards, and a telemetry information data class, are utilised by the Evaluator to implement the rewards class. This ensures that the rewards function generated by the Evaluator seamlessly integrates with the rest of the software. Various information, including episodes, rewards, fuel consumption, and reasons for episode terminations, is logged throughout the training process. This data is then leveraged by the Evaluator agent (Task 2) to assess training quality, identify issues, and refine the rewards function, as depicted in Listing 2.

Figure 3: Proposed method - decision making with LLM Agents in-the-loop.

Algorithm 1: Agentic Workflow

Task 1: Knowledge extraction - Interpreter

Required: Lunar lander’s manual

Output: Key information about flight parameters

while not finished evaluation do

Task 2: Rewards definition and refinement - Evaluator

Required: (*evaluation* = 1) Task 1 output

Required: (*evaluation* > 1) Training observations from Task 3

Output: Rewards function

evaluate inputs;
implement rewards function;
return rewards function and reasoning;

Task 3: RL training

Required: Rewards function from Task 2

Data: α : learning rate, γ : discount factor, ϵ : a small value for ϵ -greedy

Result: A Q-table containing $Q(s,a)$ pairs defining optimal policy π

Output: Training observations

*/*For each step in each episode calculate the Q-value and update the Q-table*/*

foreach episode do

foreach step in episode do

Choose action a using policy;
Take action a , observe reward R and state s ;
Compute Q function;
if s is terminal **then**
| break;
end

end

end

end

The CSV content shows that the RL agent often ends in the state 'Landed at an angle' with a varying amount of fuel used. I notice that although the agent is encouraged to use minimal fuel, it seems to be using quite a bit. There’s an opportunity to adjust the rewards to further encourage fuel efficiency. The current reward function could be more sensitive to the amount of fuel used. Also, the agent doesn’t seem to be penalized for landing at an angle, which should be discouraged. Reasons for changes:
1. 'FlightState.LANDED': The reward was modified to be more sensitive to the amount of fuel used. This is to encourage the agent to use less fuel, as we observed from the CSV file that the agent is using a considerable amount of fuel.
2. 'FlightState.LANDED_AT_ANGLE': A new condition was added to penalize the agent for landing at an angle, which was not being

addressed in the original reward function. This will encourage the agent to aim for a vertical landing.

Listing 1: Evaluator agent thought process.

```
class ImprovedGpt4RewardService (AbstractRewardService):
    def get_reward(self, telemetry: Telemetry) -> float:
        if telemetry.state == FlightState.LANDED:
            # Encourage minimal fuel usage
            return 1000 - 2 * telemetry.fuel_used
        elif telemetry.state == FlightState.OUT_OF_FUEL:
            # Discourage running out of fuel
            return -1000
        elif telemetry.state == FlightState.CRASHED:
            # Discourage crashing
            return -1000
        elif telemetry.state == FlightState.DESCENDING:
            # Encourage controlled descent
            return 100 - 0.5 * abs(telemetry.surface_velocity_z)
        elif telemetry.state == FlightState.SURFACE_CONTACT:
            # Encourage gentle landing
            return 500 - 0.5 * abs(telemetry.surface_velocity_z)
        elif telemetry.state == FlightState.LANDED_AT_ANGLE:
            # Discourage landing at an angle
            return -500
        else:
            return -1000 # Discourage other states
```

Listing 2: Rewards function provided by the Evaluator agent.

Listing 1 provides an example of output from the evaluator agent, featuring GPT-4, and its iterative process for enhancing the rewards function. This process is based on the insights gained from prior training sessions. Moreover, zero-shot prompting is applied throughout this study.

3 Results

3.1 Cumulative rewards

Figure 4 illustrates the episodic cumulative rewards obtained during the training process with the rewards function generated by three different LLMs. The average reward curves are overlaid on the same plots. While the reward functions and reward values differ across these models, the primary objective of this comparison is to illustrate the convergence behaviour of each model. Therefore, focus should be placed on the trends and patterns indicating convergence in each plot.

All plots display ascending curves that plateau towards the end, suggesting learning progress by the RL agent. However, due to the reward definition, the RL agent may converge to a stable policy corresponding to a flight state that is suboptimal. For example, in the initial training session with rewards generated by GPT-3.5 Turbo, the RL agent tends to ascend or bounce off the surface of the Moon instead of landing (as illustrated in Figure 5). Thus, the cumulative reward plots serve as good indicators of RL training performance.

3.2 Analysis of RL Agent’s Performance with LLM-Generated Reward Functions

This subsection presents an analysis of the RL agent’s performance guided by reward functions generated using three distinct LLMs. The performance metrics here are quantified in terms of the percentages of actions (*Crashed*, *Ascended*, *Landed* and *Landed at Angle*) during the convergence stage of training, as depicted in the stack bar chart in Figure 5.

The initial training run of GPT-3.5 Turbo with an unoptimised reward function favoured ascending, with minimal successful vertical landings and occasional angled landings. After evaluation, the crash rate increased, indicating a degradation in performance compared to the initial run. The agent ceased to execute any vertical or angled landings. This decline suggests that the reward adjustments disrupted the agent’s initial learning balance, reducing overall task success.

In the initial training run with rewards generated by GPT-4, the RL agent did not crash, but predominantly achieved angled landings. After evaluation, the RL agent’s performance improved notably, with a significant increase in successful landings. This progression illustrates a complex dynamic where evaluation significantly altered the reward landscape, indicating that refinement of the reward function led to substantial enhancements in the RL agent’s performance, especially in landing manoeuvres, for GPT-4.

It is evident that each LLM produces reward functions that result in distinct behaviours by the RL agent. GPT-3.5 Turbo showed potential initially, however its performance degraded after evaluation. In contrast, GPT-4 presented more nuanced learning behaviours, showing the capability to adapt and improve after the execution of the Evaluator process. In the initial training run, Llama-3-70B showed a balanced behaviour similar to GPT-4, but with an unfavourable distribution of actions. Since both GPT-3.5 Turbo and Llama-3-70B demonstrated inferior performance compared to GPT-4, this preliminary study focused on refining the reward mechanisms for GPT-4. A detailed analysis will be a topic for future work.

3.3 Fuel efficiency analysis

This analysis compares the fuel usage across the initial training and the evaluation sessions of the RL agent using rewards functions generated by GPT-4. The histogram plot in Figure 6 depicts the frequency of the amount of fuel used in KSP units across training for landing instances (one unit is the equivalent of 5 kilograms of fuel).

Figure 4: Cumulative episodic and average rewards plots for different LLM-generated reward functions.

Figure 5: Comparison of results for different LLMs.

The average fuel used for the initial training session with GPT-4’s initial reward function for landing instances is 23.7 units. However, after refining the rewards function based on evaluation, the average fuel usage significantly decreases to 15.3 units. This improvement in fuel efficiency is notable, with a reduction of approximately 35.5% in fuel consumption following evaluation. The RL agent trained with the refined rewards function demonstrates a more efficient use of fuel resources during the landing process. The decrease in fuel consumption can be attributed to the refinement of the rewards function and the inclusion of rewards which depend on fuel usage, which allows the RL agent to learn the landing strategies while also conserving fuel.

4 Discussion

Overall, this study highlights the need for refined reward functions to guide the RL agent effectively towards the desired behaviour of successful landings. Comparative analysis reveals that GPT-4 shows nu-

Figure 6: Fuel efficiency results for GPT-4.

anced learning behaviours and the most significant improvement after reward evaluation and refining, achieving higher success rates in landings compared to other models. Fuel efficiency analysis demonstrates a significant reduction of 35.5% in fuel consumption with the refined rewards function, indicating more efficient use of resources during landing.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study introduces a unique collaborative approach between LLM Agents and Reinforcement Learning, aiming to minimise the need for human intervention during the RL learning process, by utilising LLM Agents for high level strategic reasoning and code-writing. Unlike prior work where reward functions were predefined or refined using optimisation algorithms, this approach relies solely on the LLM’s capabilities to analyse the training environment and improve the rewards.

The presented results pave the way for further exploration of LLM-RL collaboration in complex decision-making tasks. Future plans include gathering more data for the current analysis and extend-

ing research into trajectory optimisation and hazard avoidance, combined with computer vision.

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